

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

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SNF, Open-Research-Data-Vorgaben

Use Case

Noor Burhan is researching the effects of the 2008 financial crisis on Swiss industrial companies. Noor Burhan is working with material from company archives and conducting qualitative interviews with company employees. The files and data from the company archives contain trade secrets, so while the companies are willing to let Noor Burhan analyze the materials, he is not allowed to publish them. And only some of the interviewees have consented to publishing their interviews, as they contain questions about their professional careers and some do not want this information to be made public. Although all direct identifiers will be removed from the transcripts in the project, the interviewees still fear that people from their professional environment could identify them.

The project is funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF). According to the SNSF's Open Research Data Policy, research data generated in the framework of a funded project are expected to be made publicly accessible at least by when the publications based on them appear. Does the SNSF require Noor Burhan to share all the data?

Does research data from SNSF projects always have to be published?

Research funding from organizations such as the SNSF requires that supported researchers make all the data that their publications are based on publicly accessible whenever possible. However, when considering whether and under what conditions data can be published, one must take into account legal and ethical considerations, confidentiality clauses, and so on. To ensure the protection of the individuals concerned, you may not publish personal data that cannot be anonymized if you have not obtained consent to publish them. The situation is similar with trade secrets or materials that are subject to copyright. In addition, ethical considerations can also speak against publishing research data.

This means that in cases where there are legal, ethical, or contractual restrictions regarding the publication of data or works, these must be respected and explained in your data-management plan.

What can you do if data cannot be shared openly for legal or ethical reasons, for example?

In principle, not all sharing is the same. For example, you can make all the data immediately and publicly accessible to all on a repository, or you can define different conditions for viewing the data. Some repositories offer specialized solutions in this regard, and they may be a possibility for sharing sensitive data. For the social sciences, for example, SWISSUbase offers options for publishing research data with different access restrictions. But independent of possible access restrictions, you must always obtain consent to publish nonanonymized personal data. Depending on the wording of the informed-consent document, it may, for instance, only be possible to share the data on request and with a use agreement. Alternatively, the [consent](#) document may only allow you to enter metadata about the datasets on a public repository, and you will then have to store the data in an encrypted form on a secure and regularly maintained university server.

What are metadata and what advantages do they offer when data cannot be shared?

Metadata are data about data. Classic metadata are, for example, author, title, location, and date. For studies in the empirical social sciences or history, it may be possible to include more precise descriptions such as the time, place, and length of interviews, the number of study participants, or the survey or interview method. With keywords and subject headings, you can characterize the content and categorize it thematically, without having to disclose sensitive details about the study participants.

Even if datasets cannot be shared publicly, metadata can help document basic information about them, about the study design, and about the methodology of the research and publications. In this way, you can publish basic information about data and register the existence of studies or data without distributing the data themselves on the Internet. This allows a dialogue with other experts, increases the visibility of your own research, can lead to more citations of your publications, and represents another entry on your own publications list.

Specialized repositories such as SWISSUbase offer input masks for describing data in detail according to subject-specific standards. On less specialized repositories, such as [Zenodo](#) or institutional repositories, there are usually additional open-ended fields in which specific metadata can be entered in an unstructured manner.

What does that mean for this case?

Noor Burhan cannot publish the data from the company archives or the interview transcripts since they cannot be completely anonymized. However, when publishing the final monograph, Noor Burhan enters metadata about the study on the SWISSUbase repository. It is possible to provide a detailed description of the data according to the standards of empirical social research in the entry on SWISSUbase, and Noor Burhan used those same standards as an orientation for conducting the research. Noor Burhan saves the transcripts in an encrypted folder on a university server. After some time, Noor Burhan is contacted by a researcher who has come across the metadata entry on SWISSUbase and is interested in using the original data for their own research project. Since some of the interviewees gave their consent for their interviews to be used for scientific purposes in other projects on request, the researcher can sign a use agreement drawn up by Noor Burhan and can then receive this partial dataset in a secure manner.